

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D2.1

CLUSTERING WORKSHOPS: LESSONS LEARNED AND KEY TAKEAWAYS

Summary:

Deliverable 2.1 will provide a compilation of 'snapshots' highlighting the problems addressed in the workshops, potential or actual solutions and recommended good practices.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Sustainable Management in the Extractive industries (SUMEX), will ultimately compile and gather exemplary sustainable practices in extractive industries in an online repository. A sustainability framework (Deliverable 1.2) has been developed to identify these practices within other projects and industry practices. Clustering is a key part of this process. SUMEX consists of five core areas: Socio-economic and Environmental Impact Assessments, Land Use Planning, Health & Safety, Permitting and Policy Integration, and Reporting Official Statistics. Between the two workshops, all focal areas have been addressed.

The theme of the first clustering workshop, *Uptaking sustainability: from research to reality*, was aimed at compiling good practices for practitioners. This workshop was an online event from 15-16 June 2021 and consisted of three sessions. The first session featured four ERA-MIN projects; the second one was a panel discussion of experts from South Africa, Canada and the United States who are affiliates of the European Federation of Geologists (EFG); and the third one featured four Horizon 2020 projects. A total of 112 people registered, with approximately 110 participants total in the three sessions. This workshop covered two of the five SUMEX focal areas: Socio-economic and Environmental Impact Assessments as well as Health & Safety.

The presentations for the first clustering workshop can be accessed at the SUMEX website <https://www.sumexproject.eu/2021/06/28/sumex-clustering-workshop-collecting-best-practice-considerations-from-european-and-global-partners/>.

The theme of the second clustering workshop was *Sustainability outside the box: lessons from natural resource projects, architecture and E-learning*. While the first clustering workshop was more traditional in substance, this workshop sought to be more exploratory, venturing beyond the conventional view of sustainability in the extractives industry by looking at different sectors and disciplines. Beyond knowledge exchange and networking, the aim of the webinar was to challenge the current thinking around the sustainability of the extractives industry by looking at good practices through different lenses, including those of non-extractive projects, architecture and E-learning. This workshop was also an online event with two sessions on 29 September 2021. A total of 116 people registered and there were approximately 80 participants in both sessions. It covered the remaining three focal areas of SUMEX: 1) Land Use Planning 2) Permitting and Policy Integration and 3) Reporting Official Statistics.

The presentations for the second workshop can also be accessed at the SUMEX website <https://www.sumexproject.eu/2021/10/12/sustainability-outside-the-box-lessons-from-natural-resource-projects-architecture-and-e-learning/>.

For the second workshop, a graphical illustrator was contracted to record the proceedings graphically. The two recordings are shown in the figures below.

The two graphics can be accessed at the following link:

<https://www.sumexproject.eu/2021/10/12/sustainability-outside-the-box-lessons-from-natural-resource-projects-architecture-and-e-learning/>

In addition, there are two videos of Sophia drawing that can be accessed at the SUMEX website:

<https://www.sumexproject.eu/2021/10/12/sustainability-outside-the-box-lessons-from-natural-resource-projects-architecture-and-e-learning/>

2 OBJECTIVES OF THE CLUSTERING WORKSHOP REPORT

Rather than being a literal summary of the five different workshop sessions, this deliverable presents a compilation of ‘snapshots’ highlighting the problems addressed in the workshops, potential or actual solutions and recommended good practices. These are provided in bullet-point format for simplicity and easy to understand points. The panel discussion of EFG affiliates (first Clustering Workshop, session two) is presented in a more detailed format due to the description of the good practices.

3 METHODOLOGY

The projects invited to present at the Clustering Workshops were identified through the screening process WP2 conducted for T2.1 Meta-Analysis and Inventory of Extractives and Related Projects.

WP2 screened *Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials H2020 Work Programmes 2014-2015, 2016-2017 and 2018-2020* as well as *MIREU D9.1* (covering projects from Interreg, EIT Raw Materials, relevant Horizon projects, ERC Consolidator Grants and projects funded by ERA-NET). The projects and call descriptions were screened with a qualitative data analysis tool, NVIVO, to find relevant subcalls and projects in the fields of extractives, climate, waste, water innovation, Earth Observation, plus policy and innovation. In the screening process, SUMEX’s thematic areas- Socio-economic and Environmental Impact Assessments, Land Use Planning, Health & Safety, Permitting and Policy Integration, and Reporting Official Statistics- were used as ‘nodes’. A node is a collection of references about a specific theme or case.

To narrow down the results and find relevant projects that align with SUMEX’s definitions of sustainability in the extractives industry, a second screening of the above-mentioned documents was conducted using SUMEX sustainability criteria (D1.2, p. 18) as well as an additional list of equivalent search words and nodes. After the second screening was conducted, the coding reports from NVIVO were extracted and the results from the two screenings were merged to capture all relevant subcalls.

The coding reports extracted from NVIVO refer to H2020 subcalls further used as search words to identify relevant projects in the Cordis database. A comprehensive list of EU level projects was compiled and later supplemented with relevant projects suggested by SUMEX Consortium partners. Screening of MIREU D9.1 provided an initial list of regional level projects. In addition, any relevant projects identified through personal networks of SUMEX Consortium partners were subsequently added to the list.

The first SUMEX Clustering Workshop aimed to gather a group of projects that addressed two of SUMEX’s core areas: Socio-economic and Environmental Impact Assessments and Health & Safety. The second clustering workshop focused on projects addressing the remaining three core areas: Land Use Planning, Permitting and

Policy Integration, and Reporting Official Statistics. However, there was an additional dimension to this workshop of looking at good practices in the extractives industry through non-extractive lenses. Hence, the two sessions were primarily oriented around contemplating the concept of 'territory' and E-learning.

For both clustering workshops, the screening process results were used to identify the projects that would be invited as presenters. For the first workshop, the emphasis was not only substance but time as well in that we wanted to primarily focus on active projects (only the ReminE project had ended). For the second workshop, time was not the issue. The idea was to feature projects funded at the regional level that tend to be more focused in scope and bring in new voices to the extractives discourse, such as those from the architecture profession. E-learning became the topic of the second session as SUMEX is now beginning to compile information for the repository component of the digital toolkit and identify the needs and users for its E-learning modules. Ultimately the projects selected for the two workshops were based on the screenings as well as the purpose of the workshop sessions. The invitation list with project coordinators' and other invitees' contact information was compiled. A registration form was created in Google Forms. WP2 included an Informed Consent Letter and a Participant Information Sheet attached to the registration form.

WP2 organised preparation calls with presenters, speakers, and moderators three weeks in advance for both clustering workshops. The invitations for the audience were sent out around the same time to give invitees two weeks to register. The detailed agenda with a Webinar link was sent out five days before the workshop.

4 WORKSHOP 1- UPTAKING SUSTAINABILITY: FROM RESEARCH TO REALITY

The theme of the first clustering workshop, *Uptaking sustainability: from research to reality*, was aimed at compiling good practices for practitioners. The workshop was an online event from 15-16 June 2021 and there were three sessions. The first featured four ERA-MIN projects; the second was a panel discussion of experts from South Africa, Canada and the United States who are affiliates of the European Federation of Geologists; and the third featured four Horizon 2020 projects. A total of 112 people registered and there were approximately 110 participants combined in the three sessions. As mentioned previously, this workshop covered two of the five SUMEX focus areas: Socio-economic and Environmental Impact Assessment as well as Health & Safety.

Session 1 (39 registrations) featured four ERA-MIN projects: LIGHTS, nanoBT, ReminE, and REVIVING.

Session 2 (33 registrations) featured one of the SUMEX partners, the European Federation of Geologists (EFG) and their affiliates, including representatives from the American Institute of Professional Geologists, the Geological Society of South Africa and Geoscientists Canada.

Session 3 (40 registrations) featured four Horizon 2020 projects: GoldenEye, NEMO, NEXT and PACIFIC.

4.1 SESSION 1: ERA-MIN PROJECTS

Four ERA-MIN projects were featured:

- Lights - Jean Cauzid, Université de Lorraine; Alexandre Lima, University of Porto; Ana Claudia Moreira Teodoro, University of Porto

- nanoBT - Nicolas Kalogerakis, Technical University of Crete; Georgios Kolliopoulos, Université Laval
- REMinE - Lina Hällström, LTU
- REVIVING – Paula Morais and Rita Branco, University of Coimbra

Figure 3: Slide from Lights presentation (Alexandre Lima and Ana Claudia Moreira Teodoro)

Lights (Lightweight Integrated Ground and Airborne Hyperspectral Topological Solutions) uses remote sensing to aid in locating new resources, such as Lithium, particularly in large geographic areas. The Lights project aims to fuse data at all scales in near-real-time with artificial intelligence algorithms to speed up the exploration process at the target scale.

nanoBT (Nano-bubble technologies) research contributes to the recovery of water and metals based on climate- and phytoremediation-driven technologies. It develops new sustainable zero-waste extractive metallurgy processes to recover residual metals and finance the remediation by exploiting the power of nanobubbles to solve a mega billion cubic meter aqueous waste problem. The research includes the development and testing of high capacity nanobubblers.

Treatment of effluents (tailing ponds) – recovery of water and residual metals (WP3)

- protect the environment
- safeguard health and prosperity
- reduce accidents and liabilities
- provide access to clean water
- tailings valorization

Figure 4: Slide from nanoBT presentation (Nicolas Kalogerakis and Georgios Kolliopoulos)

Figure 5: Figure from ReminE presentation (Lina Hällström)

ReminE (Improve Resource Efficiency and Minimize Environmental Footprint) uses the historical mine site of Yxsjöberg in Sweden to test the remining approach as a remediation method for the EU-critical elements Be, Bi, F and W. These tailings were deposited between 1928 and 1963 and have been stored open to the atmosphere with many chemical processes ongoing. The remaining concept involves excavating tailings deposited in the past and extracting and processing them in a plant to come up with minerals such as Scheelite ultimately. It is possible to extract 88% of silicates which helps to reduce the waste. The metals which cannot be extracted will be stored properly.

REVIVING (Revisiting mine tailings to innovate metals biorecovery) uses knowledge from previous ERA-MIN projects such as BioCriticalMetals. Its focus lies in valuing the mine tailings as resources, supplying metals extracted today by other processes. The aim is to promote recycling and reduce the number of tailings that exist in active mines. The approach is to understand the microbiome inside the tailings and use it to bioleach the tailings by not moving them to reduce the number of metals and toxicity.

Figure 6: Slide from REVIVING presentation (Paula Morais and Rita Branco)

4.1.1 LESSONS LEARNED AND KEY TAKEAWAYS

LIGHTS

Benefits of remote sensing (RS)

- RS can help overcome the limits of satellite data and to complement field data and field work.
- RS reduces time and costs, and in LIGHTS, allowed the identification of pegmatites in an area with low vegetation coverage.
- Satellite RS can help reduce the area in which exploration activities are conducted.

Social acceptance

- The project also includes a geo-ethical case study of lithium in Portugal as there is a lot of resistance. The key for acceptance is to inform and work with local people to inspire confidence in what is happening.

- The research team included and informed them about the exploration activities they were conducting.

Circular economy

- The mayor made the mine conditional on having local processing facilities, which will provide more and better jobs downstream.

nanoBT

Ecosystem regeneration of existing tailing ponds

- Develop novel sustainable zero-waste extractive metallurgy processes to recover residual metals and finance the remediation. These technologies will clean up the contaminated lakes that account for a few billion cubic meters around the globe and produce clean water, valorise the tailing ponds, and reduce industry-related accidents and associated liabilities due to tailing dams' problems can potentially contaminate the environment.
 - Goal is to move toward zero-waste while also financing new remediation technologies.
- Experimenting with phytoremediation and phytoextraction using halophytes and nanobubbles.
 - Recover water and metals based on climate and phytoremediation-driven technologies.
 - Part of the research aims to develop a new paradigm of processing whereby these tailing ponds/extraction effluences containing a great deal of water, heavy metals and contaminants should be thought as yesterday's news.
- Exploit the power of nanobubbles to solve a mega billion m³ aqueous waste problem
 - Two different methods are being used: 1) The first method is to treat aqueous excavation wastes with cold CO₂ nanobubbles to recover clean water in the form of ice-like products (i.e. gas hydrates) to get clean water from effluents and tailings prior to discharge. 2) The second method is to stop entirely the effluence from being used. To use low-cost, biodegradable, green, anhydrous solvents to selectively recover metals and minimize waste generation as well as water and acid consumption.
- While the energy intensiveness is similar to conventional reverse osmosis processes, the proposed technology uses similar pressures to recover the water at low temperatures, close to zero Celsius and without using a membrane.
 - The proposed technology has the advantage of a significantly wider operational window in terms of the concentration of contaminants it can treat.
 - The freezing energy is also free for several months per year in many remote locations where mineral extraction takes place in Canada and other Northern parts of the world.

Social acceptance

- One of the aims is to make extraction activities socially acceptable in Europe. This all comes down to access to safe and clean drinking water and sanitation.

Turning research into an applicable tool for industry

- The business side of it must make sense to the mining industry, meaning two things 1) it needs to be energy efficient and cost effective and 2) there has to be certainty a project can receive its permits and move forward.
- There should be stakeholder agreements with nearby supportive communities so everyone understands what is to happen.
- There should also be close government collaboration.

ReMINE

Benefits of re-mining

- Positive aspects are that it provides economic benefits for companies and the EU in terms of ensuring critical raw material supply and social and environmental benefits for the community.
- It can be used as a remediation method if all metals are extracted, including secondary minerals and scavenging metals, and the new waste is environmentally safe.
 - Need to consider volume of waste, mobile processing plants and legislation.

How to kick-start re-mining

- Many companies consider the social license as the most important aspect of re-mining.
- Need to push the environmental and social approaches of re-mining is economically difficult to make given the costs and inefficiencies.
- The financial profit from re-mining could partly help offset the remediation cost.

Potential for re-mining in Europe

- It depends largely on which metals we are targeting.
 - For example, tungsten has been extracted for a long time due to applications during war times (in ammunition) but is found in tailings due to inefficient extractions techniques and therefore has the potential to be re-mined.

Environmental mineralogy and environmental forensics

- Environmental mineralogy combines chemistry and mineralogy.
- Environmental forensics is about tracing pollution to the source.
 - The minerals are tracked back to the source with isotopes and metal concentrations.
 - ReMINE showed that some minerals are coming from other deposits in the country, and if this was not known, the environmental problem could not adequately be addressed.
 - This is particularly important for sustainable mine water and waste management.
 - This also helps determine the weathering phase, show the geochemical environment leaching out, and help choose the correct remediation technique.
- By combining chemistry with mineralogy, a schematic figure was created to understand the tailings.
 - This turned out to be important, because even though the ponds were there for a long time, only a small part has been weathered so far and it is those elements that are leaching out and creating ongoing environmental consequences.

Legislation addressing re-mining

- In Sweden, the legislation is not updated towards re-mining as it only considers whether something is an ore (mining) or remediation (not mining).
 - Sweden is, however, trying to solve the problem.
- There are no other known examples of re-mining legislation in Europe.
- It is possible, however, to change legislation and an example was given concerning ash dumps.
 - Originally ash dumps were classified as hazardous waste. Later the EU classified them as non-hazardous and legislation was subsequently changed with the result that ash dumps are now used as building material.

REVIVING

Bioleaching of tailings

- The aim is to enhance metals recovery through recycling of residues from tailing sites in two phases:
 - Phase I studied micro-organisms as leaching agents to clean residues.
 - Phase II is to see if metals can be selected.
 - Pilots will be undertaken with the Panasqueira Mine in Portugal.
- The approach is to understand the microbiome inside the tailings and use it to bioleach, reducing the number of metals and the amount of toxicity.

Social acceptance

- Although the goal is to use the toxicity of residues for alternative purposes, and this is mostly seen as positive by the public, there is some resistance to new technology.
- Factors that are anticipated to increase social acceptance include:
 - Minimize the environmental risks posed by existing mine tailings and other metal residues
 - Reduce the amount of hazardous excavation waste that needs to be disposed of
 - Provide new processes for the sustainable reprocessing of tailings
 - Provide a model pilot that will facilitate technology transfer to other mine tailings
 - Enable EU industry access to alternative sources of critical materials stemming from European locations.

4.2 SESSION 2: EFG AND AFFILIATES

Session 2 featured three panelists, all of whom are affiliates of the European Federation of Geologists:

- **Tania Marshall**, vice president of the Geological Society of South Africa (GSSA)
- **Andrea Waldie**, CEO of Geoscientists Canada, an umbrella organisation that brings together all the provincial geoscientists in the country
- **Aaron Johnson**, Director of American institute of Professional Geologists.
- **Vitor Correia**, representing the European Federation of Geologists (a partner in SUMEX) was the moderator and also presented the European vantage point.

The session focused on good practices primarily outside of Europe and the panelists were asked to provide good practice examples that reduce environmental and social impacts and/or improve health and safety.

4.2.1 LESSONS LEARNED AND KEY TAKEAWAYS

Five distinct categories of good practices emerged:

Education on the benefits of good environmental practices: In South Africa, continuous education is needed for those at the corporate level of extractive companies and the workforce itself. All levels of company staff must see the financial benefits of good environmental practices, not only the board and the executives, but also mine managers, middle management and workers. Beyond this, they must also see the benefits of good practices for them personally and for the local communities.

Turning to Canada, there are existing educational tools available online - Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada's toolkit e3 Plus: A framework for Responsible Exploration, Mining Association of Canada's toolkit Towards Sustainable Mining and Engineers Canada's Sustainability in Practice short course. Engineers Canada has also published a National Guideline on Sustainable Development and Environmental Stewardship for Professional Engineers. The Mining Matters Program in Canada, funded by companies and developed for school children, is important because it forges the connection between people's usage of raw materials and the raw materials themselves.

A comparison was drawn between awareness raising in Canada and the need to raise awareness in Europe. For 40 years Europe has had an active and successful environmental and conservation policy, and nature in Europe could be protected because raw materials needs were outsourced. This contributed to enlarging the gap between the needs and perceptions of where materials are originated. The argument is being made that suddenly there is more competition globally and Europeans need to reconsider mineral extraction in Europe, so they should forget what was said before and resume mining. Changing 40 to 50 years of ideology and policy to something completely different takes time. Still, it also takes action, energy and tools and these are not forthcoming in any significant way in Europe.

Communication and transparency: Better communication, transparency and close collaboration with communities are the keys to success. Communities should be encouraged to share their views on good sustainable practices.

Consultation is embedded in South-African policies meaning a company has to demonstrate it has spoken with all interested and affected parties to get an extraction permit. There is also legislation requiring companies to look at the social impacts of extractive operations and not only the environmental impacts. A "no extraction" option is included in the Environmental Impact Assessment.

In Canada, the idea of diverse engagement is important because it facilitates a variety of viewpoints and input to provide informed decisions. Diversity includes those on the board, a company's employees, contractors and stakeholders. Communication and transparency are not just listening to and hearing people but taking it in and embracing it and working with it. Community engagement is a matter of lengthy consulting, engaging and revising. *Raglan Mine* in Northern Quebec is cited as an example of good community engagement, as are PDAC's e3 Plus Guidelines and its 8 key principles for responsible exploration. The e3 Plus guidance contains specific actions and tools for consideration during all levels of exploration. Canada has good programs with proven success, but these did not happen overnight. They took a long time to develop and involved a tremendous amount of communication, developing panels and continuous collaboration. Implementing the best practice of the moment is not enough; we should embrace risk and innovate.

People also do not always connect technology or other things in their daily lives with mineral extraction, so *PDAC's Mining Matters group*, *APGO Education Foundation*, the *Canadian Geological Survey* and other organisations in Canada are undertaking public outreach to inform the public on these aspects and the importance of geoscience. The Canadian government is now developing the *Pan-Canadian Geoscience Strategy* and part of that has to do with public outreach and communication.

In the US, what is crucial is the importance of transparency at all levels in both the public and private sectors, "making your metrics public, so everyone knows where you stand". The public needs to see that the information they receive is valid and that decisions are not being made behind closed doors. Transparency also includes involving stakeholders in the decision-making processes. Different views help to guide the

industry towards better decisions. An example is given from the *Upper Peninsula mine in Michigan*. An extraction company arranged public on-site visits to show how the extraction site operates and how the environmental aspects were taken care of. It is important to involve all different interest groups; this particular area is on First Nations' land, an important cultural and religious place, and a popular place for hunting and fishing activities. Therefore, bringing all groups to the conversation is important.

In addition, practices evolve all the time and what was considered a good practice years ago might not be a good practice in the 2020's. When people think about the environmental problems extraction activities create, their impression is often connected to the old technologies and practices. It is difficult to prove that the extractive industry has changed from the old days; transparency and communication are the keys to winning back the public's trust. It is also important for the local community to see that the company is investing in the community. If the company benefits local communities by building parks, schools, operating scholarships and supporting the community in other ways, it is easier to earn their trust and support. Community engagement takes time and resources – both financial and know-how. Underestimating how much effort it takes to build good relations and build trust are common mistakes. The community engagement process has to be planned in advance.

Health and safety: In South Africa, health and safety in extraction sites have been priorities for many years. There is continuous risk assessment with a dedicated anonymous safety hotline where ordinary workers can call in safety tips or safety issues and these are then investigated. Education on health and safety is very advanced, as evidenced in the launch of a digital mining laboratory/simulated mining environment where users are introduced to potential accidents, problems, and risks to avoid these accidents happening in real life. Most of the extraction sites have also introduced *collision awareness and avoidance systems*. These proximity detection systems are attached to each vehicle. Sometimes they are also portable, so people carry them around. The extractive industry is working with vehicle manufacturers to develop trackless extraction machinery solutions to identify potential problems such as underground collisions. In South African mines, there is a "carrot and stick" approach: while there are multiple safety awards and recognitions, there are also 'sticks' such as the *Section 54 Shutdown Notice*. This means that if there is a fatal accident or a significant event in an extraction site, the authorities may shut it down for up to 21 days to find out where the potential problems are and to make sure there are no further risks.

Legislation and regulation: South Africa is behind the curve on environmental and social impacts but legislation is being developed. There is no distinction between Federal and State levels and this is seen as a strength. South Africa is now just trying to sensitize miners to the importance of impacts. The problem is at the mine level and middle-management because their education is outdated. *Samcodes Standards Committee (SCC)* is doing a great deal of education and training.

In Canada, geoscience as a profession is highly regulated. There is a legislated code of ethics and it covers health and safety as well as the environment.

Concerning legislation, transparency is also key to see what is being done and if it works. The USA has many different levels of regulatory agencies. The federal legislation regulating mining is the US mining law from 1976, which has not had any major changes since its inception. The Mine and Safety Health Administration at the federal level also regulates health and safety. Each state has its own regulations that vary greatly; although, most focus is on water quality discharge and underground safety. Tribal governments also have input. There are also multi-jurisdictional entities such as the Tri-state mining district in Missouri, Kansas, and Oklahoma to add to the complexity.

Uptaking good practices: To start a dialogue, a company must invite everyone who might be interested in joining their sessions. Companies should not decide what a community needs. The community tells what they need. And then the company has to say how they can help the community with that. The companies must be provided with the tools and the training on community engagement. The material has to be engaging and provide the proper knowledge so companies can be informed about issues like acuity, diversity and inclusiveness. For public outreach, on-site visits have proven to be an effective way to create the mental connection between mining and daily lives and share information on the extraction process itself. Another example is that a Canada company created an online forum and put out notices that the meetings were available. They heard what people wanted and expected and then moved towards an agreement with the community.

In South Africa, if the industry can explain the financial benefits to an individual company, if they can see the potential for more investments while also having fewer difficulties with local communities or less complications with the regulatory authorities, companies are far more likely to implement what we think are good practices.

Companies in the US are very results oriented and results driven, so the best way to convince someone that a particular practice will work is to show that it has already worked – to point to the specific examples and specific data about the project and practices. However, this also appears to be true globally. People need to see a personal application and interest in what is taking place. It is important to share positive examples and show that the extractive industry has learned from its mistakes in the past – it has developed new ways of doing things and is ready to apply the new good practices. In addition, constant repetition and ease of access seem to work for practitioners as human nature tends to shy away from change. It is also true that the very best practices have to be used early on because of the long timeframe of mining.

4.3 SESSION 3: HORIZON 2020 PROJECTS

Four Horizon 2020 projects were presented:

- GoldenEye –Sanna Uusitalo and Marko Savolainen (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland)
- NEMO - Andrea Di Maria and Lieven Machiels (KU Leuven)
- NEXT - Karin Beland Lindahl (Lulea University of Technology) and Leena Suopjärvi (University of Lapland)
- PACIFIC - Aoife Braiden (Irish Geological Survey)

GoldenEye (Earth observation and Earth GNSS data acquisition and processing platform for safe, sustainable and cost-efficient mining operations) will develop an Earth Observation and Sensing Data platform which is a toolkit for mines to monitor open pit mine slope stability, waste pile stability, tailings pond stability and underground mine activity. The platform can help those working at the mine to communicate with the local people and show they care for nature, which in turn affects social acceptance.

Field trials for piloting GOLDEN AI platform

Underground extraction in Finland:

- Pyhäsalmi deposit
- Mineralogy copper-zinc sulphide
- One of the deepest underground mines in Europe
- At the end of mine life-cycle

AIM: safety for mine re-use

- Integration of high-resolution drone data with satellite data to monitor slope integrity, both open pits and tailing ponds
- GNSS geolocation in underground mine to ensure the re-user safety

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101019388

Figure 7: Slide from GoldenEye presentation (Sanna Uusitalo and Marko Savolainen)

NEMO (Near-zero-waste recycling of low grade sulphidic mining waste for critical-metal, mineral and construction raw material production in a circular economy) will recover 95 per cent of sulphidic mining residues through the extraction of basic metals, rare earths and other critical metals. Sotkamo mine and the Kylylahti mine, both located in Finland, are the case studies. Both are developing two innovative bioleaching technologies, which are then used for enhanced metals and minerals recovery and clean material residues for recycling. NEMO addresses how technologies reduce impacts in two ways: 1) Sulphites and sulfidic tailings can generate acid mine drainage since heavy metals can be leached into the environment. There are no sulphites in the final residue with the NEMO process, so no acid mine drainage. 2) NEMO looks at bulk material to see if it can be used for construction material. If no waste is left and everything is used, there is no need to create tailings dams and incur the associated risks.

The social impact assesment

Stakeholder categories	Impact categories	Subcategories	Inventory indicators	Inventory data
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Workers	Human rights			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local community	Working conditions			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Society	Health and safety			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consumers	Cultural heritage			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Value chain actors	Governance			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Children	Socio-economic repercussions			

Source: UNEP, 2020 Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organisations 2020.

Figure 8: Slide from NEMO presentation (Andrea Di Maria and Lieven Machiels)

NEXT (New Exploration Technologies and Social Acceptance) is about developing new exploration technologies for a more efficient, economic and environmentally friendly ore exploration. The focus of the presentation is on the result of WP5: Social License to Explore (SLE) and Operate (SLO). The approach was taken to understand the importance of sensitive exploration technologies (and other factors) to SLE and SLO in three selected localities in Northern Finland and Sweden. It is important to understand the complexity and range of perspectives of local actors and communities. With respect to technologies, engaging with local communities and providing information for them is crucial for acceptance.

Figure 9: Slide from NEXT presentation (Karin Beland Lindahl and Leena Suopajärvi)

PACIFIC – (Passive seismic techniques for environmentally friendly and cost-efficient mineral exploration) aims to develop two innovative and complementary seismic techniques to discover new deposits and expand known deposits. Both approaches are based on passive seismic imagery. These techniques must have sufficient accuracy and resolution for the mineral industry, be relatively low cost, and have a minor impact on the environment. PACIFIC also conducts research on social acceptance and public perception of risk for mining activities. The focus of the presentation is on how people process online information. People need information and they go online and this can skew perceptions. Therefore, we need to provide information locally to create an accurate reference point.

PACIFIC Experiment 2: What are the “primacy effects” (influence of first arguments seen) in opinion formation related to mining, and how to mitigate these?

Figure 10: Slide from PACIFIC presentation (Aoife Braiden)

4.3.1 LESSONS LEARNED AND KEY TAKEAWAYS

GoldenEye

Golden AI platform

- GoldenEye will develop a multi-source Earth Observation and Sensing Data platform to improve mine safety, reduce mineral extraction's environmental footprint, and increase profitability. The platform is a toolkit for the extraction sites to monitor open pit mine slope stability, waste pile stability, tailings pond stability and underground mine activity. The toolkit also helps to improve the mineralogical mapping of mine site ground surfaces, mineralogical analysis of drill cores for exploration and ore processing, and the mineralogical analysis of underground mine shafts.
 - Earth Observation sensing is via satellite sources. The main targets are safety regarding ground deformation, slope stability in open pit mines, tailing dams and the environmental footprint meaning changes of ground cover and surface waters.
 - The focus of Drone (UAV or unmanned aerial vehicle) based sensing is once again on the environmental footprint, particularly on the detection of contaminated lands and vegetation, changes in land elevation, and waste pile analyses. Geophysical data will calibrate the satellite-based sensors for more accurate prediction of the 3D geology of mine sites.
 - Innovative Proximal Sensing is used for field exploration, active hyperspectral imaging, and GNSS geolocation based on cellular positioning. The aim using this approach is to get the precise location of underground mine activities.
- An open public demonstrator will illustrate the benefits of the Golden AI platform for the extractive industry and show that the output might help mines and authorities to visualize the mining environment and track the effect of the mine on the surrounding environment. Feedback from those who try the demonstrator will be used to improve the platform.
 - Most importantly, it allows miners to see benefits immediately. Miners at the site are the focus of the project but typically see technology as something that complicates their lives because it is unknown. No one wants to be the first to uptake a new technology and instead prefer to wait until it is proven.

Improve social acceptance

- The mines in the case studies use platforms to discuss with people what their concerns are, for example, if they are worried about nature around the mine and the environmental footprint.
- A media toolkit will be developed for outreach purposes at each of the mine sites.

NEMO

Innovating bioleaching technologies

- Pregnant Leach Solutions (PLS) ponds are an integral part of heap leaching technology and used to collect and contain heap leaching related solutions. The PLS is then used to recover metals in the three pilot plants.
- Clean Matrix technology is used to valorize nonmetal mineral waste in the three pilot plants. It is then used for the construction industry. Alternative cement and aggregates are produced.

Sustainability Analysis

- The project uses three types of Sustainability Analysis which are combined and integrated into a multi-criteria assessment:
 - Environmental life cycle analysis (E-LCA)
 - Social LCA (S-LCA)
 - Economic Life Cycle Cost (LCC)

Social Impact Assessment

- Aims to find stakeholder categories (workers, local communities, society, children) which are most at risk, and quantify impacts using working hours as the main parameter.
- The SIA will use a clear metric to define social impacts and integrate local data into the analysis.

Communicating social findings

- Challenging because do not want partners to see analysis as a threat but as an opportunity.
- The social is about how to minimize risk and avoid impact. For example, if metals are recovered from waste, this avoids production of metals from other sources. There are impacts you can avoid, and these become benefits.
- Communicating the benefits to extraction companies is not so difficult, but communicating to the general public is much more complicated.

NEXT

Definitions of sustainable development

- Everybody wants sustainable development, but people tend to understand and mean different things with it.
- The understanding of sustainable development by local people differs a lot and powerfully shapes attitudes to exploration, mining and technology.
- NEXT and other research have provided three sets of attitudes:
 - more jobs and growth
 - care for nature
 - develop and diversify
- In places where actors emphasize the need for jobs and growth, there is a strong dependence on mining and attitudes tend to shift towards a positive view.

Individual values

- The formation of attitudes is based on individual values.
- These values differ between people, organizations and contexts.
- What seems to be most important is the perceived balance. People balance future economic benefits of exploration or a possible mine, and their fear and anxieties about negative environmental or social impacts.

Importance of local context/knowledge

- Timely information and high-quality company-community engagement are important and can affect attitudes.
- Respectable behaviour and consultation are key.

- Local knowledge varies, but for the most part, exploration and exploitation are understood as interlinked, and peoples' attitudes tend to be the same toward both. People who are positive towards mineral extraction are usually also positive towards exploration and vice versa.
- Although attitudes toward mineral extraction are complex, we can now identify the more general factors driving positive and negative attitudes. This is extremely beneficial for a company both in deciding whether or not to enter a high-risk area, or simply to recognize those factors when they enter a new area.

Role of policy makers

- For policy-makers, understanding how attitudes are formed can enable a more coherent policy framework, ensuring clear rules for everyone, which in turn helps to avoid conflicts.
- It is also important to realize that some value-related trade-offs have to be determined on a political level. Policy makers have to help all actors and players by providing clear frameworks and mechanisms for making trade-offs.

Technologies

- Perceptions of technologies depend on what people and what technologies. In NEXT, local actor perceptions depend on the extent to which the company has informed the citizenry. Organised actors were generally well informed.
- Less intrusive technologies are welcome but other factors are more important.
- Switching technologies will not make an already negative population more positive to exploration or exploitation in a nature conservation area. It is all about using it sensibly.
- How impacts are perceived depends on the contexts and lifeworlds of different actors, and how they are affected by mineral extraction. What technology can accomplish hinges on the livelihoods, needs and understandings of sustainability of the different actors. This also relates to how the technologies are used and where they are used.
- Attitudes toward extraction activities do not depend so much on technology but the perception of impacts that would follow with a possible extraction site.
- Environmentally sensitive technologies reduce the environmental footprint of exploration but are not very important to local attitudes.
- With new technology, information has to be provided to local communities about its benefits, in conjunction with a company also understanding the complex meanings and understanding the range of different perspectives of the local actors.

Health and safety

- Regarding health and safety, exploration is not in itself associated with major health and safety risks; rather, exploration activities give rise to uncertainty about the community's future development.
 - In particular, there is anxiety about environmental risks or expectations about economic benefits associated with a possible mine development.

How to communicate project findings

- There is no one way or one tool to share information from the NEXT project with a wider audience. A range of different strategies have to be used.
- NEXT will launch a digital toolkit for companies.
- For local communities, digital tools have limitations and it is more effective to go to communities and communicate what has been done.

PACIFIC

Analysing public perception of risk

- Two key aspects are included:
 - GSI, a generalized survey to assess opinion on mineral extraction and exploration in Ireland
 - ESRI, computerized experiments to assess how people comprehend information, assess risk and make decisions, specifically what is the physiological mechanism involved?
 - Engaged experts in behavioral psychology and neuroscience. Topics studied: opinions on mineral extraction in general, knowledge of mining in Ireland, perceived benefits/risks of mining, experience of exploration for minerals, regulation of extraction activities and demographics.
- The research questions:
 - Does the method of online information provision affect people's comprehension of extraction-related activities and the impacts to their local area?
 - Tested theory that self-led learning leads to improved comprehension
 - Does the method of online provision affect people's evaluation of that information?
 - Tested the strength of influence of the first argument seen. Can opinions be changed?
 - Do the effects of the method of online information provision depend on the source of that information?
- The results:
 - In Ireland most people are in the middle.
 - Some people do not even know that there is a mine in Ireland even though it is the second biggest lead and zinc mine in Europe.
 - The linear form of presenting information is better, as people tend to spend a little more time going through it.
 - The first information people get will influence and form their opinion and that it is very difficult to change afterwards.
 - All of this is used to improve how information at the national and public level is being presented.
 - The results also show that too much time has been spent with people at the end of the spectrum rather than with those in the middle.
 - Ultimately the results were most beneficial because they enabled those in the PACIFIC project to better communicate and discuss their findings with colleagues on the policy side of the geological survey.
 - It also became clear that the expertise of those you are working with has to be respected as the methods and knowledge of different disciplines are vastly different.
 - Find the right person for a job and do not remake people to fit roles they are not supposed to be doing (engineers may not be the best people to conduct community outreach and build collaborative partnerships).

Tool to communicate project results to a wider audience

- The ability to tailor results to the audience being addressed and to provide a broad spectrum of examples.
 - For instance, rather than merely showing good practices, it is more helpful to also provide examples of mines (visual is better) with problems, how they are different from 'good practice' mines and how those problems will be mitigated.

5 WORKSHOP 2 – SUSTAINABILITY OUTSIDE THE BOX: LESSONS FROM NATURAL RESOURCE PROJECTS, ARCHITECTURE AND E-LEARNING

The theme of the second Clustering Workshop was *Sustainability outside the box: lessons from natural resource projects, architecture and E-learning*. Of the five core areas of SUMEX, this workshop covers Land Use Planning, Permitting and Policy Integration and Reporting Official Statistics. While the first clustering workshop was more traditional in substance, this workshop sought to be more exploratory in nature, venturing beyond the conventional view of sustainability in the extractives industry by looking at different sectors and disciplines. Beyond knowledge exchange and networking, the webinar aims to challenge the current thinking around sustainability of the extractives industry by looking at good practices through different lenses, including those of non-extractive projects, architecture, and E-learning. This workshop was also an online event with two sessions on 29 September 2021. A total of 116 people registered and there were approximately 80 participants in the two sessions.

Session 1 (62 registrations) featured three regional-level projects that provided different perspectives on what good extractive industry practices mean: REGINA, BuSK and Malagueira.

Session 2 E-learning (54 registrations) also featured three projects but focused solely on E-learning: HiTech AlkCarb, RM@Schools, and DigiEcoQuarry.

5.1 SESSION 1: CONTEMPLATING 'TERRITORY' – LESSONS FROM NATURAL RESOURCE AND ARCHITECTURE PROJECTS

The first session of the second SUMEX clustering workshop focuses on extractive activities through different lenses. The REGINA project shows the community and municipality perspective of mining. The BuSK project focuses on mining through different nature-based resource projects. Malagueira is an architecture and social housing project. This new approach should challenge the idea that the extractives industry's good practices only come from the extractives industry. During the workshop, a graphical illustrator summed up the key points of the projects and possible interconnections. The good practices gleaned from these projects will be integrated into a toolkit that will form the basis of capacity building to teach what good practices are in the context of sustainable mineral extraction.

Three projects were presented:

- REGINA – Leena Suopajarvi, University of Lapland
- BuSK - Mikko Jokinen, Natural Resources Institute Finland
- Malagueira - Pedro Guilherme, University of Évora

The EU funded the **REGINA** (Regional Innovation in the Nordic Arctic) project through its Northern Periphery and Arctic Programme. REGINA aims to reduce the vulnerability and increase the preparedness of small remote communities in the Nordic Arctic and Scotland facing either the development or withdrawal of large-scale, resource-based industries. The project focuses on the municipality of Sodankylä's response to the mining boom, which started in Finnish Lapland around 15 years ago. Sodankylä is in the middle of Lapland where multiple mining developments are proposed. Not only did these developments come en masse but they also came quite suddenly for the municipalities, who realized they were not prepared to handle multiple big projects that would clearly affect the nearby communities significantly. In particular, it was realized the way social

Social sustainability in Sodankylä Municipality's mining programme

SODANKYLÄ MUNICIPALITY'S MINING PROGRAMME

SOCIAL IMPACT MANAGEMENT AND EVALUATION PLAN 2020, 2023, 2026, 2029

SECTION	GOAL, OBJECTIVE	ACTION PLAN	INDICATOR
SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welfare of people living in the community increases Villages close to mining projects can benefit out of the mining projects The negative impacts and losses are minimized and compensated Local culture has good ability to act and develop Traffic safety increased New residents settling into the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of different livelihoods so that there are job and education opportunities for whole families Road and pedestrian way investment and improvement projects Social impacts are evaluated and followed up and problems solved: local mining forum established Housing and accommodation improved Facilitation of "Local Mining Forum" for impact follow-up and problem and possibility solving on municipality level together with stakeholders and industry Support for new inhabitants to settle in Sodankylä Cooperation with national-level networks such as Finnish Network for Sustainable Mining 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The results of follow up survey for local people, every second year, about the experienced impacts of mining Number of inhabitants, male/female ratio, % of persons working at mine registered in the municipality Traffic safety increased: less accidents and less experienced unsafety Cooperation agreements on voluntary basis with different actors, such as mining forum

Figure 11: Slide from REGINA presentation (Leena Suopajärvi)

impact assessments were routinely conducted did not adequately address and mitigate the problems affecting the host communities, especially in the area of cumulative impacts. Social impact assessments are made in the planning phase when there are not yet impacts; hence, it is more akin to a forecasting exercise. Instead, they should be used to analyse, monitor, and manage an action's intended and unintended social consequences.

BuSK (Building Shared Knowledge), funded by The Northern Periphery and Arctic 2014-2020 Programme, has developed planning tools that enhance the use of participatory techniques. Livelihoods in the region are largely dependent on natural resources and land, and issues around land use often are contested by various stakeholder interests, BuSK combines science- and experience-based knowledge that assists decision makers with land use planning and natural resource governance.

Attitudes towards expansion: no-go areas

- 21 respondents draw 26 different (no-go) areas that they think are not suitable for mining
- The amount of answers is low for this question and it doesn't tell about the general attitudes towards expansion
- Data shows an example of the areas where the division of the opinions of acceptance of mining can grow

Figure 12: Slide from BuSK presentation (Mikko Jokinen)

Malagueira (Património de Todos, Subsídios para a sua classificação) is a housing development designed by the Portuguese architect Álvaro Siza Vieira in the 1970s and has been recently included on the recent national indicative list of UNESCO World Heritage sites. Malagueira is an urban expansion plan, west of the old city center of Évora, in an old vacant agricultural farm. By 1976 the new elected municipality wanted a plan to include 1200 dwellings, public buildings, and parks to cope with the need for housing and re-design the connections to illegal neighbourhoods. Ultimately only the housing was built and the site remains unfinished. Malagueira is distinct because it successfully addresses difficult land use issues many large scale projects are

forced to grapple with: the growing urbanization of rural areas, the construction of a new neighbourhood in coexistence with an old city, and the then new phenomena of popular participation during Portugal's revolutionary period (1974-1980). Malagueira's recent tentative listing spurred a project led by the University of Evora to identify, recognise and systematise the values associated with tangible and intangible cultural heritage and promote MALAGUEIRA.PT as a new brand that integrates cultural, architectural, historical, social and scientific values.

Figure 13: Slide from Malagueira presentation (Pedro Guilherme)

5.1.1 LESSONS LEARNED AND KEY TAKEAWAYS

REGINA

Differentiating between environmental and social impacts

- The difference between environmental impact and social impact is that environmental impacts affect human life, lifestyle, or habits that turn into social impacts.
- If the environment changes, life also changes.
- People from local communities share the view that environmentalists enter their communities to lecture them even though they do not understand the surrounding area.

Social Impact Management Plan (SIMP)

A SIMP manages the impacts identified in a Social Impact Assessment and is typically developed in partnership with regulatory agencies, investors and the community.

- Sodankylä undertook a collaborative process that included a baseline analysis, three stakeholder workshops, and a seminar open to the public to comment on the SIMP.
- The final result adopted by officials is the Social Impact Management and Evaluation Plan.
- The scope concentrated primarily on how benefits and burdens that affect nearby villages can be balanced and the burdens compensated.

Difficulties with implementation

- The municipality is responsible for local development, but the problem is that there are many sectors that need to be involved in the implementation of the SIMP and are not, namely the social, health, environmental and technological sectors.
- In small municipalities, it is difficult to get everyone committed to the SIMP.
- In Sodankylä, there have also been disputes at the local level among politicians and other stakeholders.
- A good practice would include getting all relevant government authorities to cooperate and commit to implementing the SIMP.

Remaining Challenges

- Not that much has happened in the last year of the program period (2021) because the municipalities lack monetary and personnel resources in small, rural communities, which hinders the developmental work.
- There is no "ownership" for social sustainability as the range of social impacts is very wide.

BuSK

Capacity building

- Especially important in remote and sparsely populated communities, all stakeholders were involved in land use planning and natural resource use decisions.
- Use of participatory GIS for collecting local knowledge about land use planning and for decision makers as it combines diverse kinds of knowledges.

Measuring well being

- With the help of interviews, surveys and data collected from GIS, information about the well-being of the local population in relation to Kittilä mine site was gathered.
- Residents felt that well-being has been strengthened and trust for the future was high (61.1%).
- Positive emotions towards mining are often linked to job opportunities (negative emotions are linked to traffic).

Delineating no-go areas

- People were asked to draw no-go areas on a map. The results show that 21 respondents drew 26 different (no-go) areas that they think are not suitable for mining.

Local context matters

- While the Kittilä mine is considered mainly positive among residents and neutral for tourist companies, there are real differences in opinions. Well-being and positive impacts are not allocated equally.
- Every mining case is unique and making parallels between cases is easily misleading. The attitudes towards potential new mining projects were rather hesitant.
 - 45,5% agree that it is enough to have one mine in Kittilä but 22% disagree.

Fair allocation of costs and benefits

- A good practice for mining companies and municipalities is to pay attention to the fair allocation of costs and benefits, and indeed, it would be difficult to get a social license to operate without it.

Demand for change

- NGOs and individual citizens have an essential role in demanding change but also perhaps too much responsibility.

Trust in mining authorities

- The surveys included an evaluation of whether mining authorities are trusted.
 - In Kittilä, the majority (54.9%) think controlling and monitoring mineral exploration and running a mine should be stricter.
 - Only one in five think current level of control is sufficient.
- Regarding trust, some mining cases have been quite problematic when it comes to environmental impacts and management, which is why the trust in mining authorities has collapsed.

Malagueira

Social issues

- Poverty and lack of knowledge, which creates fear and further produce violence
- The lack of value in the Malagueira housing development, which is the origin of stigma. Malagueira is internationally known for having a high urban and architectural quality but has never been finished and lacks the involvement of both the public and inhabitants.
- Need for participation and empowerment and the idea of common good

Who demands change

- Residents want better living conditions

- Architects and urban planners, who want to protect the urban and architectural object
- Public partners want fewer problems and to qualify (free of charge) the municipal urban areas for the UNESCO designation
- Public in general because they understand how Evora as a World Heritage site was improved from 1986 onward

Who is open to awareness raising

- Everyone is open to new knowledge if someone takes the time to explain things
- All of the inhabitants want to know more about where they live

How to raise awareness

- Exhibitions and conferences were used to explain and foster the project and the architect by showing Álvaro Siza's drawings and produced models.
- Inhabitants were empowered through knowledge and the creation of a network of partners.

Lessons for SUMEX

Mining as humanized territory

- The architecture of Malagueira pays attention to the site's topography and the development of mines and quarries needs to as well.
- One of the defining features of Malagueira is the protection of the exceptional natural elements of the site, including the water courses and the existing natural landscape that is typical in Alentejo. Extractive activities also have to protect exceptional natural elements around the project site and should look to architecture for new ideas regarding conservation and preservation.
- Both architecture and mining seek to increase the resilience and biodiversity of nature. Malagueira does this through an urban park, which can serve as a blueprint for similar conservation ideas for extractive projects.
- Landscape, architecture and urban space mingle together in a humanized territory of incredible natural and cultural beauty. Malagueira stands visually linked to the historic city center and an extraction site should be connected with its surroundings.

How to raise awareness about mining

- Produce content about mining comprehensible to those outside of the industry
- Explain and innovate
- Disseminate and connect
- Include and cooperate and foster relations
- Adapt and change and keep trying
- Redo previous steps

KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM THE GRAPHICAL RECORDING

Figure 14: Graphical recording from the second Clustering Workshop, session 1 (artist: Sophia Halamoda)

The role of money: Within every project, one of the prevailing themes is money. In REGINA and Malagueira, there were many plans that ended up being scuppered due to lack of funding. In the first case, while the SIMP was adopted, it was not implemented. In the second case, Malagueira remains unfinished as no money remains for the envisioned restaurant and other commercial uses. In BuSK, a large part of the acceptance of mining was due to possible job opportunities.

Implementation: While authorities and municipalities are responsible for ensuring responsible mining, they often neither have the monetary resources nor can physically do everything themselves. Help from citizens, those in the local community and residents is needed.

Collaboration: Participation from community members as well as cooperation between residents, companies and government needs to be increased

Fairness : Although 'fair' is not defined, conceptually, everyone understands the importance of being fair to all.

Knowledge: All projects talk about knowledge and learning as being a necessary and continuous process.

Local context: Every mining project is unique and it is challenging to extrapolate good practices from site to site. The local context is the framework and also benchmark against which good practices are measured.

Short-term versus long-term land use planning: Municipalities and regional authorities tend not to address the issues of short-term versus long-term land use planning even though a mine is both. They typically look at a mine as a short-term land use planning issue.

Finnish Lapland is a very large rural area. It is assumed that there is room for every livelihood, but when looking at the map, it can be seen that this is not the case. It is likely that there will be more environmental conflicts coming.

Closure : Many people do not care what happens after 20 years because it is too abstract. It is very important to look at the afterlife of projects and consider what happens after extraction in an area stops. One of the key issues is what is left behind by environmental projects and what happens to the actual site. For example, is the site to be rebuilt or re-naturalized and what happens to the mining waste left behind and other damages that may have occurred. It is crucial to work with a community to understand their vision post-mining.

Industry thinking: Industry's thinking has changed a great deal in the past 20 years, and they are in the midst of shifting to a sustainability and land-use mode of thinking.

5.2 SESSION 2: E-LEARNING

This session focused on E-Learning since SUMEX will produce a digital toolkit which has an E-learning component. The aim is to glean help from the projects in the clustering workshop to avoid redundancies and fill gaps.

Three projects were presented:

- HiTech AlkCarb - Kate Taylor Smith (Camborne School of Mines, University of Exeter)
- RM@Schools - Armida Torreggiani (National Research Council of Italy)
- DigiEcoQuarry – Lorena Viladés Santos (ANEFA – National Association of Aggregate Manufacturers and Entrepreneurs)

What was most successful?

- **Social and active learning increases the possibility of learners completing the course**
- **Films** are top engaging content, especially from 'real life' – factories, exploration sites
- Simple 'virtual fieldtrips' / case studies engaged students well too
- Internet bandwidth can limit accessibility of videos (e.g. Africa)
- Learners praised opportunities for interaction with educators – so if you can afford **facilitation** or some sort do consider it.
- Activities we tried:
 - mentimeter word clouds,
 - research info sharing via Padlet,
 - quizzes,
 - polls,
 - lots of discussions,
 - reflections

Figure 15: Slide from HiTech AlkCarb presentation (Kate Smith)

What formats of MOOCs and online exchanges are most successful?

iTech AlkCarb (New geomodels to explore deeper for High-Technology critical raw materials in Alkaline rocks and Carbonatites) finished in 2020 and was funded under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme to develop new geomodels and sustainable exploration methods for alkaline igneous rocks and carbonatites. In January 2020, HiTech AlkCarb launched its Technology Metals for a Green Future MOOC, which teaches how critical raw materials are found and used and allows users to explore their role in contributing to a more sustainable future. The project focuses on technology metals needed for the green transition, including rare earths, tantalum, niobium, tin, tungsten, and lithium.

RM@Schools (Raw MatTERS ambassadors at Schools) is one of the two Flagship Programs in the Wider Society Learning segment of EIT RawMaterials. It supports the RawMaterials Academy's efforts towards young students (11-19 years old) across Europe to promote a wide dissemination action on raw materials-related themes in schools and society through strategic European partnerships among research, university, school and industry. RM@Schools has created a significant amount of content and toolkits for schools and promotes an extensive range of actions towards society to promote sustainability and circular economy strategies. Raw MatTERS Ambassadors at Schools is an innovative program to make science education and careers in RM attractive for youngsters, involving RM experts and teachers.

Set up of a succesful e-learning activity

Figure 16: Slide from RM@Schools presentation (Armida Torreggiani)

DIGIECOQUARRY (Innovative Digital Sustainable Aggregates Systems,) having just started in June 2021, takes a coordinated approach towards construction materials management to achieve the goal of reducing EU external supply dependency while also using resources more efficiently. For their E-learning activities, DigiEcoQuarry will develop a Capacity Building Program that provides knowledge and tools for practitioners in the following areas: video tutorials on how to use the platform for company owners, technical staff and site

workers, one Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) on digitalisation in the aggregates industry and three training sessions on the use of the platform (video conferences). The main goal of DIGIECOQUARRY is to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarring System (IGS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated digitalized automatic and real-time processes for aggregates quarries. This will upgrade health and safety, enhance selectivity and profitability of the aggregates sites, maximize sustainability and resource efficiency and improve social acceptance through communication with policy makers, citizens and relevant actors.

Figure 17: Slide from DIGIECOQUARRY presentation (Lorena Viladés Santos)

5.2.1 LESSONS LEARNED AND KEY TAKEAWAYS

HiTech AlkCarb uses FutureLearn, which is a platform offering online courses typically four to six weeks long and free of charge. The five-week online course is intended as a dissemination tool for HiTech AlkCarb's researchers, but the impetus behind its development is the growing anti-mining sentiment and concern around mining. The researchers saw a lack of awareness of where raw materials come from and a resulting disconnect with the end products of technology.

Purpose of an online course

- There are several reasons why people develop an online course. The project used the courses for research dissemination and networking.
- It can also be helpful to increase awareness for non-university learners and is particularly advantageous for educational purposes. People that cannot attend have the chance to learn online.

Identifying target groups

- To define target groups, five key messages were identified, ten audience groups, and four secondary messages.
- The key message to get across was a particular learning object for each week that provided information to people to think about how mining and exploration can be greener in the future.
- People in mining were already engaged through other courses, journal articles, etc. The challenge is reaching people outside of this bubble, for example, those who use social media. Making the resources accessible is key.

Selecting and designing tools

- The content of the MOOC is based on the themes that emerged when identifying the audience, and the tools were developed around those themes. Specific tools include:
 - Key questions are covered in the course
 - Quizzes after the course
 - Engaging videos
 - Virtual fieldtrips

Attracting users

- Used multiplier organisations, newspaper articles, social media, press releases -, to raise awareness of the course.
- Most of the effort was put into making the course rather than attracting users. In addition to the above, professional association networks such as the Critical Minerals Association were used, but mostly, the team relied on word of mouth.
- In hindsight, the team should have dedicated more money to find other dissemination means. Continually marketing the project would have kept participant numbers up.

Continuous engagement during the course

- Students need to be actively engaged to take part and both films and simple virtual field trips are beneficial.
- It is important to have a clear organization and structuring of the course content, very interactive tools and not to overload participants.

Measuring the impact of E-learning tools

- Within the course, students were asked their opinions on specific themes before they started the course and at the end of the course. Their responses were compared to see if there was a change.
- At the end of the course, there is an option for students to participate in a survey that provided a great deal of feedback. (Quite often, people answered that they did not know there were so many raw materials.)

Pitfalls to avoid

- The course was preset, so there were not enough active moderation and engagement opportunities.

RM@Schools: Raw Matters Ambassadors at School

Purpose of an online course

- The purpose of RM@Schools is to introduce students to topics related to raw materials and in particular, to the European Union's challenges around raw materials.

Identifying target groups

- Pupils from 10-18 years
- Teachers

Selecting and designing tools

- A successful e-learning platform can be set up by choosing an objective, a learning method, and assessing the chosen objective.

- The most important way to learn is through ‘doing’.
- The aims of the toolkits and tools are to be engaging and put the students in situations where they would actively engage with and contribute to the topics to learn.
- The project provided a virtual center with easy access to all the toolkits divided by areas, for teachers to use in the future.
- The toolkits are freely available on an e-learning platform (MOODLE) and include:
 - experimental activities/kits
 - digital tools
 - educational games (RAWsiko)
 - discussion tools
 - videos
- The tools use different learning methodologies such as learning-by-doing, digital learning, gamification and role playing.
- Each toolkit is associated with three documents:
 - A summary with all key information of the activity
 - A teacher’s card, which explains all details to realize the activity
 - A student card, which drives pupils to do the experiment and understand the science behind it
- Additionally, some videos regarding webinars on-demand or tutorials are available on YouTube.
- One of the most successful toolkits is gamification. During the pandemic, the project released a game called RAWsiko- Materials around us.
- A website where the toolkits are available and social media is being used to share the learning pathways and teaching materials.

Attracting users

- It is essential to understand different points of view.
- It is also important for people to choose what they would like to learn and how long the course can last.
- Demonstrate effectively how to engage kids and people outside of the expert bubble in a meaningful way.
- Go to schools directly and present the tools at conferences and publish in journals to raise awareness of the effectiveness of this approach.
- Try to involve different age groups to learn something new and open a discussion.
- Other ways to diffuse the learning material are educational conferences and science fairs.

Continuous engagement during course

- Create an active learning atmosphere, make it fun and interesting for the students.
- Engage teachers and families into the activities.
- The project proposes active learning to schools by involving students in experiments with RM-related hands-on educational kits and communication activities. The aim is to shift from information to engagement by providing more engaging experiences for everyone. Therefore, it is important to engage/empower teachers by developing educational tools for them and by creating a sense of community.

Measuring impact of E-learning tools

- If the training works well, the student becomes a multiplier of knowledge. This is measured through collaboration with a researcher who can measure whether the student’s knowledge has improved.

- All students are asked to become RM Ambassadors. Therefore, all students act as multipliers of knowledge among society. With this strategy, around 27.000 people were engaged to participate during 2018 and 2020.
- Teachers also act as multipliers by speaking to colleagues, so it is important to open a dialogue with them. Now schools are approaching RM@Schools and not the other way around.

Pitfalls to avoid

- The feedback from teachers regarding the digital toolkit is generally positive, but they also seem to find it quite challenging sometimes.

DIGIECOQUARRY

Purpose of an online course

- For industry use, a capacity building program.
 - Quarry owners and managers need to understand the advantages that digitalization will bring.
 - Quarry workers may be concerned about a high level of digitalization and what that means for their jobs. They need to understand that technology will not displace but help them.
- For local communities and civil society, engagement and awareness raising to achieve a social license to operate.
 - The social community should discover what is happening around them,
 - Make the link between quarry-related activities and the goods they use in their daily lives
 - Appreciate how the quarry manages the environment and contributes to the community
 - Raise general awareness
 - Improve the perception of the extractive industry

Identifying target groups

- The two target groups for training and e-learning purposes are 1) quarry owners, managers and workers and 2) local communities and civil society.
- Identifying the right people is a challenge, effective outreach methods and tools are needed.

Selecting and designing tools

- The capacity building programme for industry is envisioned to be ‘full service’ – trainings, technical sessions and workshops to learn to use the various tools.
 - Focus groups with quarry owners, managers and workers to define/refine the training programs.
 - Video tutorials (i.e. IQS tutorial)
 - Massive Online Open Course
 - Digitalisation advantages and how to improve quarry management
 - Video and text formats
 - Online interaction between learners and teachers via discussion forums
 - Online tests
 - IQS simulator
 - Virtual workshops and round tables with third parties on digitalisation advantages
 - Other tools (infographics, etc.)
- For gaining an SLO, tools include:
 - Focus groups with stakeholders to define/refine the training programs
 - Online surveys to ask for input/feedback.

- Explanatory videos of the activities and environmental management
- Online workshops to introduce aggregates as well as the environmental and social aspects
- Local stakeholders will also be asked if there are things of specific interest they would like to cover.

Attracting users

- Highlight the benefit for users in their own context
 - For example, quarry owners and managers are interested in increasing efficiency
 - Workers want greater health and safety
 - Civil society wants to learn about activities and see they benefit from them
- Contact all stakeholders directly, whether they are from the local communities or the quarry owners and workers).

Continuous engagement during course

- Course has not been designed yet.

Measuring impact of E-learning tools

- The hope is that quarry workers directly approach the researchers and mention that the digital toolkit has been helpful for them.

Pitfalls to avoid

- The major concern is over language and effectively reaching the target audience and communicating as people speak different languages.

KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM THE GRAPHICAL RECORDING

Figure 18: Graphical recording from the second Clustering Workshop, session 2 (artist: Sophia Halamoda)

Enthusiasm: The most important thing when talking about engaging people or education is enthusiasm which is a simple recipe for success.

Communication and outreach: Another point which affects all three projects, shareholders and perspectives is communication. It is how you approach stakeholders from different backgrounds, industries, and age groups to address diversity. This is where the challenge lies when looking at education. One of the key points during the HiTech AlkCarb presentation was the collaboration with key stakeholders. When it comes to outreach, people are a broadcaster and a receiver by proving a digital toolkit that collects data.

Social License to Operate: Listening is important when communicating and educating local stakeholders to get a social license to operate.

Customization: In terms of e-learning covid has been a catalyst. For example, the virtual field trip is an event to draw people in by customizing it to the target group.

Asynchronous learning: Another important aspect is an asynchronous learning aspect where people can learn at their own pace which allows to customize to different needs.

Celebrate successes: Networking, collaborating and celebrating successes helps to encourage educational support for e-learning.

Need for more dialogue: To influence policy back to the education and e-learning sector it needs to communicate the impact which is created. It comes back to the direct engagement of people; the dialogue is the main tool to achieve anything on any level. There is still a lot to improve in the e-learning sector.

6 CONCLUSIONS

6.1 SNAPSHOTS OF BOTH WORKSHOPS

There are several repeating themes that can be seen in both workshops:

- **The role of technology in building social acceptance.** The ERA-MIN and Horizon projects, in particular, focused on this nexus and what came through is that people's views of and responses to, technology are conditioned by who these people are and what the technologies are used for. In terms of the presenters, those who come from an engineering background see very clearly the benefits of the technologies they are developing and believe whole-heartedly that once the public understands the benefits, they too will be warmly receptive to the technologies. Conversely, social scientists see technology as simply one factor among many that need to be understood and factored into the benefits versus burdens equation of social acceptance. The studies on social license to explore carried out by the NEXT project further emphasised the complexity around how attitudes toward mining are developed and what it takes to change those attitudes.
- **Tools for uptaking technology.** The moderator in the first clustering workshop asked the presenters directly what tool would be needed for companies to uptake the technologies discussed. The answers were rather ambiguous. It was clear that 'selling' companies on technology is much easier than convincing the general public they are beneficial enough to alleviate all of their concerns. What was also notable is that there is no one tool that will help uptake, if talking about a company, or acceptance if talking about the general public. Instead there needs to be a suite of tools and approaches for both groups that should be tailored to whoever the audience is.

- **Health & Safety.** This does not appear to be an issue that concerns communities or the public but rather an internal matter for companies. In the EFG session, it was obvious that South Africa has put a great deal of effort into this issue, whereas it was not as prominent in Canada, the US or Europe.
- **Political will and money.** Perhaps the most prominent lesson from the first session of the second clustering workshop is the importance of political will and money. In REGINA, the municipality had enormous momentum to develop and adopt a Social Impact Management Plan. Still, after years of work, it continues to lie dormant. Malagueira remains unfinished after over 40 years due to a lack of both. In BuSK, a large part of the acceptance of mining was due to possible job opportunities.
- **Building a community of practitioners.** Over and over again, it was emphasised that active engagement and ensuring those who are engaged become multipliers is crucial to the success of an E-learning program. There also appears to be more competition for an 'older' audience who are mainly practitioners; yet, the excitement around E-learning revolved around young students and teachers as targeted by RM@Schools. A successful E-learning program requires consistent and constant engagement (and advertising), which poses a challenge for projects which have an end date and no longer have a budget for this type of effort.

7 APPENDIX 1

7.1 AGENDA FOR FIRST CLUSTERING WORKSHOP

Agenda for Virtual SUMEX Clustering Workshop 15-16 June 2021

The theme of the clustering event is: Uptaking sustainability: from research to reality and the objective is to discuss and obtain good practice examples for practitioners.

Two of five SUMEX focus areas are covered: 1) Environmental and Social Impact Assessment and 2) Health and Safety.

Tuesday, 15 June

Session 1: ERA-MIN projects

o Time: 10-11:30 CET

o Moderator: Sarah Gordon, SATARLA and Responsible Raw Materials

o Projects:

- LIGHTS: Jean Cauzid (Université de Lorraine), Alexandre Lima (University of Porto), Ana Claudia Moreira Teodoro (University of Porto)
- nanoBT: Nicolas Kalogerakis (Technical University of Crete), Georgios Kolliopoulos (Université Laval)
- ReminE: Lena Alakangas (Luleå University of Technology)
- REVIVING: Paula Morais (University of Coimbra), Rita Branco (University of Coimbra)

Discussion Topics: How can technologies from the ERA-MIN projects reduce environmental and social impacts? What is their potential for uptake by companies?

Session 2: EFG and affiliates

o Time: 14-15:30 CET

o Moderator: Vitor Correia, European Federation of Geologists

o Panelists:

- Aaron Johnson, American Institute of Professional Geologists
- Tania Marshall, Geological Society of South Africa
- Andrea Waldie, Geoscientists Canada

Discussion Topic: Global perspectives – what are your top 3 good practices for reducing environmental and social impacts and/or improving health and safety?

Wednesday, 16 June

Session 1: H2020 projects

o Time: 9-10:30 CET

o Moderator: Sarah Gordon, SATARLA and Responsible Raw Materials

o Projects:

- GoldenEye: Sanna Uusitalo (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland), Marko Savolainen (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland)
- NEMO: Andrea Di Maria (KU Leuven)
- NEXT: Karin Beland-Lindhal (Luleå University of Technology), Leena Suopajarvi (University of Lapland)
- PACIFIC: Aoife Braiden (Geological Survey Ireland)
- TARANTULA: Lieven Machiels (KU Leuven)

Discussion Topic: Is there a gap between how people perceive technology and what it actually accomplishes on-the-ground? Is health and safety still seen as an issue in Europe?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101003622

7.2 AGENDA FOR SECOND CLUSTERING WORKSHOP

Agenda for the 2nd Virtual SUMEX Clustering Workshop 29 September 2021

*Sustainability outside the box: lessons from natural resource projects, architecture and E-learning
Featuring graphic illustrator: Sophia Halamoda*

This is the 2nd and last Clustering Workshop for the SUMEX project. The 1st featured ERA-MIN projects, a discussion between affiliates of the European Federation of Geologists and Horizon 2020 projects. Good industry practices were the focus and the themes were two of SUMEX's core areas: environmental and social impact assessment plus health and safety.

This second workshop is more exploratory in nature, venturing beyond the conventional view of what sustainability in the extractives industry means by looking at different industries and disciplines. The challenges the extractives industry of today faces are increasingly broad in scope and bringing different views and voices to the discourse is crucial to address these challenges.

Beyond knowledge exchange and networking, the aim of the webinar is to challenge the current thinking around sustainability of the extractives industry by looking at good practices through three different non-extractive lenses.

- The first lens is regional identity and transformation and looks at mining in conjunction with other natural resource projects, particularly the responsibility companies and policy-makers have to ensure consistently better company practices on the company side and good land use planning and natural resource governance on the authority side.
- The second lens looks at the concept of 'territory', specifically a social housing development in Portugal, and how architecture and land use planning can contribute positively to natural and humanized landscapes.
- The third lens engages participants on the topic "moving from data to knowledge management" through E-learning honing in on 1) what is important and should be emphasised, 2) what are the technical and process aspects of learning including how to motivate people, and 3) how to garner the attention of decision-makers?

Extractives projects are not homogenous and, consistent with the composition of the SUMEX project partners, both aggregate and metal projects are in focus. Again, this is the last of two clustering workshops for the SUMEX project and addresses its remaining three core areas: 1) land use 2) permitting and policy integration and 3) reporting

Wednesday, 29 September

Session 1: Contemplating ‘territory’ – lessons from natural resource and architecture projects

Time: 10.00-11.30 CET

- o Moderator: Katharina Gugerell, (University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna)
- o Respondent: Pedro Guilherme (University of Évora)
- o Projects:

- REGINA: Leena Suopajarvi (University of Lapland)

The aim of the REGINA (Regional Innovation in the Nordic Arctic) project, funded by the EU as part of the Northern Periphery and Arctic Programme, is to reduce the vulnerability and increase the preparedness of small remote communities in the Nordic Arctic and Scotland facing either the development or withdrawal of large-scale, resource-based industries. An innovative model for developing Local Smart Specialisation Strategies (LS3) was created to support local authorities, and it was tested and implemented by each of the five municipalities in the project group. REGINA also created guidance and support tools for other municipalities facing similar types of development challenges.

- BuSK – Mikko Jokinen (LUKE – Natural Resources Institute Finland)

BuSK (Building Shared Knowledge), funded by The Northern Periphery and Arctic 2014-2020 Programme, has developed planning tools that enhance the use of participatory techniques. Livelihoods in the region are largely dependent on natural resources and land, and issues around land use often are contested by various stakeholder interests, BuSK combines science- and experience-based knowledge that assists decision makers with land use planning and natural resource governance.

- Malagueira, Património de Todos, Subsídios para a sua classificação: Pedro Guilherme (University of Évora)

Included on the recent national indicative list of UNESCO World Heritage sites, the housing development of Malagueira, designed by the Portuguese architect Álvaro Siza Vieira, is distinct because it successfully addresses difficult land use issues many large scale projects are forced to grapple with: the growing urbanization of rural areas, the construction of a new neighbourhood in coexistence with an old city, and the then new phenomena of popular participation during Portugal’s revolutionary period (1970s). Malagueira’s recent tentative listing spurred a project led by the University of Evora to identify, recognise and systematise the values associated with tangible and intangible cultural heritage and to promote MALAGUEIRA.PT as a new brand that integrates cultural, architectural, historical, social and scientific values.

Discussion topics: How can looking at the concept of territory help companies gain social acceptance when they enter a new ‘territory’? What have companies learned from the REGINA project? Have authorities moved forward in reconciling and possibly aligning land use, participation and the permitting system addressed in BuSK? How can the more holistic view of the Malagueira project inform the future of planning and permitting extractives projects?

Session 2: E-learning

Time: 13.00-14.30 CET

- Moderator: Andreas Endl (Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien)
- Discussant: Patrick Nadoll (EIT Raw Materials)
- Projects:
 - **DigiEcoQuarry:** Lorena Viladés Santos (ANEFA – National Association of Aggregate Manufacturers and Entrepreneurs)

DigiEcoQuarry, having just started in June 2021, takes a coordinated approach towards construction materials management to achieve the goal of reducing EU external supply dependency while also using resources more efficiently. For their E-learning activities, DigiEcoQuarry will develop a Capacity Building Program that provides knowledge and tools for practitioners in the following areas: video tutorials on how to use the platform for company owners, technical staff and site workers, one Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) on digitalisation in the aggregates industry and three training sessions on the use of the platform (video conferences).
 - **HiTech AlkCarb:** Kate Smith (Camborne School of Mines, University of Exeter)

HiTech AlkCarb finished in 2020 and was funded under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme to develop new geomodels and sustainable exploration methods for alkaline igneous rocks and carbonatites. In January 2020, HiTech AlkCarb launched its Technology Metals for a Green Future MOOC, which teaches how critical raw materials are found and used and allows users to explore their role in contributing to a more sustainable future. The project focuses on technology metals, which are those needed for the green transition including rare earths, tantalum, niobium, tin, tungsten, lithium.
 - **RM@Schools:** Armida Torreggiani (RM@Schools)

RM@Schools 4.0 emerges from RM@Schools 3.0, the WSL (Wider Societal Learning) Flagship programme of EIT RawMaterials and is running parallel with RM@Schools-ESEE, dedicated to the ESEE (East and Southeast Europe) region. It is supporting the RawMaterials Academy's efforts towards young students (11-19 years old) across Europe to promote a wide dissemination action on raw materials-related themes in schools and society through strategic European partnerships among research, university, school and industry. RM@Schools has created a significant amount of content and toolkits for schools and promotes a large range of actions towards society in order to promote sustainability and circular economy strategies.

Discussion Topics: *How do you build and maintain a community of practitioners? What motivates people to participate in E-learning activities? How do you distil the information needed? What do you see as the gaps in E-learning that SUMEX could or should fulfil?*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101003622